

THE ACTION OF CHLORINE ON THE HYDROXIDES OF ALKALINE EARTHS IN THE PRESENCE OF IODINE. PART II.

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By passing chlorine through hot solutions of iodine in the hydroxides of the alkaline earth the corresponding iodates in hydrated form are precipitated in each case. There is no formation of periodate by the above method.

It has been found that on passing chlorine through a boiling solution of iodine in the hydroxides of alkali metals, *e.g.*, lithium, sodium and potassium, the corresponding periodates are formed (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 17, 167). This reaction has been studied in the case of the hydroxides of the alkaline earths, which have been found to yield the corresponding iodates and not the periodates. The hydroxides of calcium, barium and strontium yielded hexahydrated calcium iodate, $\text{Ca}(\text{IO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and monohydrated barium iodate, $\text{Ba}(\text{IO}_3)_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ respectively. They are all white crystalline powders.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Iodine was dissolved in a solution of the respective hydroxides (calcium hydroxide being very sparingly soluble, was taken in the form of a suspension) and heated to boiling. A white precipitate was formed in the case of barium hydroxide, a lesser amount in case of calcium hydroxide and only a milkiness appeared with strontium hydroxide. A brisk current of chlorine was then passed through the respective hot solutions of iodine in the hydroxides. There was an immediate liberation of iodine from calcium hydroxide and barium hydroxide solutions with a noticeable increase in the amount of the precipitate. In the case of strontium hydroxide there was a separation of a white precipitate followed by the liberation of free iodine. From this it appears that only a very slight amount of iodate is formed before the passage of chlorine through the solution. Chlorine takes an active part in the precipitation of strontium iodate.

In all cases most of the iodine escaped in the form of vapours and on passing more of the chlorine the solution became clear, leaving a white precipitate. It was filtered, washed and dried at 40° in the electric air oven and analysed.

Alkaline earth was determined as the corresponding sulphate. Iodine was estimated by the method given by Scott ("Standard Method of Chemical

Analyses", 1926, Vol. I, p. 244) and oxygen by Partington and Bahl's method (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 1088).

TABLE I.

Calcium salt.

Sample.	Calcium.	Iodine.	Available oxygen.
1	8'257%	50'928%	16'135%
2	8'154	51'341	16'762
3	8'593	50'863	16'463

These results agree with the formula $\text{Ca}(\text{IO}_3)_2, 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, for which the calculated value of calcium and iodine are 8'030 and 51'004% respectively. According to $2\text{Ca}(\text{IO}_3)_2, 6\text{H}_2\text{O} = 2\text{CaO} + 2\text{I}_2 + 5\text{O}_2 + 12\text{H}_2\text{O}$ available oxygen is 16'065%.

This salt was also prepared by Millon (*Ann. chim. phys.*, 1843, 9, 413) who obtained it by crystallising a mixture of a solution of calcium nitrate or chloride with iodic acid.

TABLE II.

Strontium salt.

Sample.	Strontium.	Iodine.	Available oxygen.
1	19'086%	56'087%	17'187%
2	19'007	56'143	17'778
3	19'434	56'893	17'096

These values correspond with the formula of monohydrated strontium iodate, $\text{Sr}(\text{IO}_3)_2, \text{H}_2\text{O}$, the calculated values of strontium and iodine being 19'236 and 55'756% respectively. The available oxygen according to the decomposition $2\text{Sr}(\text{IO}_3)_2, \text{H}_2\text{O} = 2\text{SrO} + 2\text{I}_2 + 5\text{O}_2 + 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ is 17'560%.

This salt was also obtained by Rammelsberg (Mellor, "A Comprehensive Treatise in Inorganic and Theoretical Chemistry", 1922, Vol. II, p. 348) by mixing together hot solutions of strontium chloride and sodium iodate.

TABLE III.

Barium salt.

Sample.	Barium.	Iodine.	Available oxygen.
1	27'661%	52'040%	16'201%
2	27'412	52'395	16'134
3	27'468	51'873	16'062

The values correspond with the formula $\text{Ba}(\text{IO}_3)_2, \text{H}_2\text{O}$, the calculated values of barium and iodine being 27.182 and 52.043% respectively. The available oxygen according to the equation $2\text{Ba}(\text{IO}_3)_2, \text{H}_2\text{O} = 2\text{BaO} + \text{I}_2 + 5\text{O}_2 + 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ is 15.830%.

Gay Lussac (*cf.* Mellor, *loc. cit.*) obtained the monohydrated barium iodate, $\text{Ba}(\text{IO}_3)_2, \text{H}_2\text{O}$ by merely dissolving iodine in baryta water. From this it is evident that chlorine has no further action on this solution.

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